

Computational phantoms for investigating impact of noise magnitude on modulation transfer function

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ABSTRACT

Accurate measurement of spatial resolution in terms of modulation transfer function (MTF) is essential in computed tomography (CT) images. The purpose of this study was to develop a computational phantom that can be used to evaluate the effect of noise on the MTF in CT images. Our computational phantoms for measuring MTF in CT were developed with MATLAB software. The phantom image was blurred by a point spread function of a certain standard deviation. Subsequently, different noise levels were added to the phantoms. Next, an automatic MTF calculation was implemented. The first step of the MTF calculation was to determine the region of interest (ROI). Profile was generated from the ROI, and a line spread function (LSF) curve was formed. The LSF curve was Fourier transformed to produce a MTF curve. Greater noise added to phantom image, it yields greater effect of standard deviation on the measured MTF. The greater noise makes the MTF curve increases differently than MTF with 0 HU noise. The 10% MTF values at the 25% noise reach more than 2.0 cycle/mm. By the developed computational phantoms, the spatial resolution and the amount of noise can be determined independently.

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1. INTRODUCTION

An important parameter which directly indicates the image quality of computed tomography (CT) is spatial resolution [1]–[3]. Spatial resolution is the ability to distinguish small objects that are close to each other [4]. It is usually presented using the modulation transfer function (MTF) with a cut-off value of 10%. The measurement of spatial resolution in CT can be manually or automatically carried out on dedicated specific phantoms, such as the American Association of Physicists in Medicine (AAPM) CT performance phantoms [5], CatPhan phantoms, or American College of Radiology (ACR) phantoms [6]–[8]. MTF can be measured from several objects, including the point spread function (PSF) [9], line spread function (LSF) [10], [11] and edge spread function (ESF) [12], [13]. The precise and accurate measurement of MTF can be used to compare the effects of different scan parameters [14], [15], reconstruction filters [16], [17], field of view (FOV) [6], [18], focal spot size [19], [20], and others [21], [22].

Although there is no theoretical relationship between noise and MTF, a previous study reported that accurate and precise MTF measurements depend on the noise level in an image [23]. High noise level causes fluctuations in the MTF, and hence reduce the accuracy and precise of the MTF measurement [24]. The image noise can be from the exposure factors [25]–[27], detector noise and quantum noise [28], quantum

detection efficiency (QDE), and geometric detection efficiency [29], [30]. Hence, many studies suggested that obtaining accurate spatial resolution should be performed at a low noise level [21], [31].

There are several studies that have attempted to measure the MTF values of noisy images [23], [32]. Mori [32] introduced a fitting technique in a noisy image with low contrast resolution, which yielded the same MTF value as the theory. Takenaga *et al.* [23] also reported that MTF measurements obtained by curve-fitting produced MTF values that were resistant to noise both in high and low contrast objects. If the fitting technique was not applied, there were many peaks on the LSF, producing high MTF values at high frequency values [32].

The quantitative effect of noise on the MTF measurement in the radiograph has been shown by Gonzalez using three artificial phantoms [28]: edge, bar, and star bar phantoms. For the edge phantom, the uncertainty was ± 0.036 , for the bar phantom ± 0.026 , and for the star bar phantom ± 0.026 at a frequency of 0.7 mm^{-1} [28]. This is evidence that noise produces a large uncertainty in the MTF measurement. However, no study reported the limit of noise level for measuring accurate and precise MTF. In this paper, computational phantoms to investigate the effect of noise level on the accuracy and precision of MTF values in CT images were developed. To achieve the goal, the contrast of the wire and background objects was varied. Based on the result of this study, the limit of noise level on accuracy and precision of the MTF will be obtained.

2. METHOD

2.1. Phantom design

We developed computational phantoms using MATLAB software. The phantoms consisted of a circular object with a diameter of 512 pixels mimicking water with a value of 0 Hounsfield unit (HU). In the middle of the phantom was a wire (point), and on the outside of the phantom was air with a pixel value of -1000 HU. If the phantom diameter was assumed to be 50 mm, then each pixel had size of $50 \text{ mm}/512=0.0977 \text{ mm} \approx 0.1 \text{ mm}$. The wire (point) size was about 0.25 mm. With this size, the spatial resolution of the CT can be detected to the limit of $1/2d$ or about 2 cycles/mm. This was enough to simulate a real physical phantom for measuring MTF because the spatial resolution of many CT machines is in the range of 0.5-1.5 cycles/mm. In this study, there were three phantoms with three different pixel values of wires, as shown in Figure 1. Figure 1(a) shows phantom with pixel value of 50 HU, Figure 1(b) shows phantom with pixel value of 100 HU, and Figure 1(c) shows phantom with pixel value of 150 HU.

Figure 1. Three computational phantoms developed in this study. Phantoms had a diameter of 512 pixels and mimicked water with a value of 0 HU. In the middle of the phantoms there was a wire (point) for measuring MTF with diameter of 0.25 mm with three different pixel values, i.e. (a) 50 HU, (b) 100 HU, and (c) 150 HU

2.2. Phantom image degradation and MTF calculation

The spatial resolutions of the computational phantoms $P(x,y)$ were degraded by convolution with a point spread function ($PSF(x,y)$), after which various levels of Gaussian noise $N(x,y)$ were added [33]. The image degradation was modeled by:

$$I(x,y) = \frac{1}{k} [P(x,y) \otimes PSF(x,y)] + N(x,y) \tag{1}$$

image normalization was accomplished by dividing the image by k , were:

$$k = \text{sum}(\text{sum}(PSF(x,y))) \tag{2}$$

The degradation process can be seen in Figure 2. Each image of a point phantom was blurred by a standard deviation of $\sigma = 0.031$ mm and various noises added from 0 HU to 25% of the wire (point) pixel value. The noise variation is shown in Table 1. Each measurement was repeated 10 times, and the means and standard deviations of the MTF curves were calculated.

Figure 2. Modeling of spatial resolution and noise on a point phantom, and the MTF measurement process

Table 1. Noise values are given to each computational point phantom

Pixel value of point phantom (HU)	Added noise (HU)					
50	0	2.5	5.0	7.5	10.0	12.5
100	0	5.0	10.0	15.0	20.0	25.0
150	0	7.5	15.0	22.5	30.0	37.5

We used automatic MTF measurement described in previous studies [34], [35]. The first step was to automatically determine the region of interest (ROI). The center of the point image was chosen as the center of ROI with size of 32×32 pixels. The profile of pixel values was created from the pixels within the ROI. Both edges of the ROI profile were zeroed by subtracting the mean value of 5 pixels on the left and right of the profile. This profile is the line spread function (LSF), which was then normalized in order to obtain an MTF with value of 1 at a spatial frequency of 0 mm^{-1} , after Fourier transformation. The 10% and 50% MTF were calculated.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. MTF without noise

Blurring is obtained by convolving the phantom image (Figure 1) and the PSF, and the results are shown in Figure 3. There are three phantoms with different point pixel values, i.e. (a) 50 HU, (b) 100 HU, and (c) 150 HU. In Figure 3, the noise in the images is 0 HU. The MTF curves for three point phantoms with pixel variations of 50, 100, and 150 HU are shown in Figure 4. The three MTF curves overlap, indicating that

the MTF curves are identical. This shows that regardless of the contrast between the point object and the background, the MTFs are identical, if there is no added noise. The values of 10% MTF and 50% MTF for the three phantoms are 1.06 cycles/mm and 0.58 cycles/mm, respectively.

Figure 3. The images of the point phantoms after blurring (second line) used to calculate the MTFs. Pixel values of the point are (a) 50 HU, (b) 100 HU, and (c) 150 HU

Figure 4. MTF curves of three-point phantoms for pixel values of 50, 100 and 150 HU with noise level of 0 HU. The MTFs of the three phantoms are comparable and overlap each other

3.2. MTF with noise

Noise levels from 0 HU to 12.5 HU were added to the point phantom of 50 HU, and the MTFs calculated Figure 5. Greater noise levels make the MTF curves fluctuate more from those without noise. This is also observed in the point phantom of 100 HU Figure 6 and in the point phantom of 150 HU Figure 7. The values of 10% MTF and 50% MTF are shown in Tables 2-4. Tables 3 and 4 shows that the 10% MTF values at the 25% noise reach more than 2.0 cycle/mm.

Figure 5. The mean curve of MTFs for the point phantom of 50 HU for noise levels from 0 HU to 12.5 HU

Figure 6. The mean curve of MTF for the point phantom of 100 HU for noise levels from 0 HU to 25 HU

Figure 7. The mean curve of MTFs for the point phantom of 150 HU for noise levels from 0 HU to 37.5 HU

Table 2. The mean values of 10% MTF and 50% MTF for the point phantom of 50 HU and for noise levels from 0 HU to 12.5 HU

Added noise (HU)	10% MTF (cycle/mm)	50% MTF (cycle/mm)
0	1.06	0.58
2.5	1.09	0.59
5.0	1.09	0.60
7.5	1.17	0.63
10.0	1.18	0.58
12.5	1.18	0.55

Table 3. The mean values of 10% MTF and 50% MTF for the point phantom of 100 HU and for noise levels from 0 HU to 25 HU

Added noise (HU)	10% MTF (cycle/mm)	50% MTF (cycle/mm)
0	1.06	0.58
5.0	1.07	0.57
10.0	1.12	0.60
15.0	1.29	0.64
20.0	1.30	0.59
25.0	>2.00	0.69

Table 4. The mean values of 10% MTF and 50% MTF for the point phantom of 150 HU and for noise levels from 0 HU to 37.5 HU

Added noise (HU)	10% MTF (cycle/mm)	50% MTF (cycle/mm)
0	1.06	0.58
7.5	1.07	0.59
15.0	1.10	0.58
22.5	1.09	0.61
30.0	1.58	0.61
37.5	>2.0	0.69

3.3. Standard deviation of MTF with noise variation

The curves of mean and standard deviation of MTFs for the point phantom of 50 HU are shown in Figure 8 with noise levels of 0, 2.5, 5, 7.5, 10, and 12.5 HU Figure 8 (a-f). They show that the more noise is added to the point phantom image, the larger standard deviation of the MTF is obtained. This is also shown on the point phantom of 100 HU depicted in Figure 9 with noise levels of 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 HU Figures 9 (a)-(f), and for the point phantom of 150 HU depicted in Figure 10 with noise levels of 0, 7.5, 15, 22.5, 30, and 37.5 HU Figures 10 (a)-(f). The error bars represent standard deviation and the blue lines are the mean value of MTFs.

Figure 8. The curves of mean and standard deviation of MTFs for the point phantom of 50 HU and various noises. (a) 0 HU, (b) 2.5 HU, (c) 5 HU, (d) 7.5 HU, (e) 10 HU, and (f) 12.5 HU. Measurements are performed 10 repetitions

Figure 9. The curves of mean and standard deviation of MTFs for the point phantom of 100 HU and various noises. (a) 0 HU, (b) 5 HU, (c) 10 HU, (d) 15 HU, (e) 20 HU, and (f) 25 HU. Measurements are performed 10 repetitions

Efforts to obtain spatial resolution accurately are very important [26]. The accuracy of the spatial resolution is affected by many things, including the amount of noise in the image. Gonzalez-Lopez developed artificial images using Monte Carlo simulation which were used to simulate the sampling, blurring, and noise processes [28]. Phantoms are used to determine the impact of noise in measuring spatial resolution in images [12]. The phantoms include the bar, edge and star bar phantom. In the current study, point computational phantoms were developed. The phantoms comprised of various compositions with pixel values from 50 HU to 150 HU. Noise up to a quarter of the pixel value of the point was added to the phantoms to evaluate its effect on the MTF value.

If a large amount of noise is added to the phantom image, it caused greater standard deviation of the spatial resolution. This result is consistent with the previous research by Gonzales-Lopez [28] using bar, edge and star bar phantoms. As a result, medical physicists should ensure that noise in the image is small when measuring spatial resolution. In practice, noise levels in the image should not be greater than 10% of the contrast value between a point object and the background. If the noise is greater than 10%, then a fitting technique, such as those proposed Takenaga *et al.* [23] or Mori [32], should be implemented.

The low noise level could be easily achieved by increasing the tube loading (mAs) or radiation dose [21], [31]. The level of radiation does not matter from the dose aspect because the scan is performed on a phantom. However, some CTs have an automatic system, so that increasing the tube loading causes the focal spot to increase so that the spatial resolution will decrease [34].

The advantage of using computational phantom is that the amount of noise can be set at will. However, the drawback is that the modeled noise may not be the same as the actual noise in a CT scanner. Moreover, the use of iterative reconstruction (IR) in CT images results in non-uniform noise. However, the Gaussian noise used in this study can still be used as a reference regarding the effect of the amount of noise

on the accuracy of the MTF value. To create non-uniform noise a circular object with various material types can be used instead of the point phantom. The MTF value should be calculated by taking into account the noise and contrast of the objects simultaneously. This is called as the task transfer function (TTF) [35]. Development of a computational phantom for TTF evaluation will be carried out in a future study.

Figure 10. The curves of mean and standard deviation of MTFs for the point phantom of 150 HU and various noises. (a) 0 HU, (b) 7.5 HU, (c) 15 HU, (d) 22.5 HU, (e) 30 HU, and (f) 37.5 HU. Measurements are performed 10 repetitions

4. CONCLUSION

We successfully developed computational phantoms to evaluate the effect of noise on the MTF. By using computational phantoms, the value of the spatial resolution and the amount of noise can be determined independently. The results show that the amount of noise affects the accuracy of the MTF. We found that for a noise value of 10% of the image contrast, the results in a significantly different MTF curve from the actual value.

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